

Analysis of the Influence of CPU Specifications on System Performance Using Linear Regression

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 06 January 2026</p>	<p>The development of computer technology demands an increase in optimal system performance, especially in the Central Processing Unit (CPU) component as a data processing center. CPU performance is affected by various hardware specifications such as machine cycle speed, primary memory capacity, cache, and number of input/output channels. This study aims to analyze the influence of CPU specifications on system performance using linear regression methods. The data used is secondary data on CPU specifications and performance processed using the RapidMiner application. The research methods include the data collection stage, data preprocessing, linear regression modeling, and model evaluation using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value and determination coefficient (R-squared). The results show that several CPU specification variables have a significant influence on system performance. The resulting linear regression model is able to predict CPU performance with a good level of accuracy so that it can be used as a tool in analysis and decision-making related to computer hardware selection.</p>
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<p>KEYWORDS: CPU, Data Mining, System Performance, RapidMiner, Linear Regression.</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of computer technology demands a quantitative analysis of the relationship between CPU specifications with System Performance so that the selection of hardware can be done objectively and based on strong statistical indicators. Linear regression is a suitable method for evaluating the influence of various CPU technical variables such as clock frequency, number of cores, and cache size on compute performance as measured through benchmark scores or program execution time. In addition, the integration of regression analysis with data mining in visual platforms such as RapidMiner allows researchers to take steps preprocessing, model design, and comprehensive performance evaluation without writing overly complex manual programs, thus speeding up the CPU data analysis process. Such analysis is needed especially in the context of modern computing systems that are constantly evolving in order to accurately map the relationship between hardware components and performance outputs [1].

Linear regression research in context data mining It has been widely applied in various fields as a tool for predicting and evaluating the relationship between input and output variables, including in the prediction of values and trends in technical and non-technical datasets. In many studies in Indonesia, linear regression is used to model the relationship between technical variables and desired outputs to produce models that can support data-driven decision-making. Stages such as data cleaning, attribute transformation, and feature

selection in regression models are essential to reduce noise and improve prediction accuracy, for example in the case of stock price predictions or other financial variables. This shows that the application of linear regression in the context of data mining with software such as RapidMiner is very useful for relating technical variables to performance outputs statistically [2].

In research data mining, the selection of linear regression as a prediction method is often accompanied by the analysis of evaluation metrics such as coefficient of determination (R^2) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) to measure the quality of the model in capturing output variability based on input variables. A high R^2 value reflects that the linear regression model is able to explain most of the variation in output data such as the CPU's benchmark performance score, while the RMSE provides an overview of the model's predictive error rate against the actual value. The combination of these two metrics is an important indicator to evaluate the extent to which linear regression models are effective in the context of computer system performance and hardware selection. This approach also provides insight for IT practitioners in assessing whether a particular CPU specification will meet the expected computing needs [3].

In quantitative research based on data mining, linear regression is often combined with forecasting evaluation techniques to compare the model's ability to predict numerical variables compared to other methods. This approach is also relevant in the analysis of computer system performance, as

it allows researchers to evaluate the accuracy of the model in predicting CPU performance based on its technical specifications. The use of evaluation metrics such as MAPE, RMSE, and R^2 helps determine the quality of regression models built from specification data and CPU benchmark results. Therefore, linear regression can be used as a valid method to evaluate and compare the performance of CPU performance prediction models quantitatively [4].

Based on this description, this study aims to analyze the influence of CPU specifications on system performance using the RapidMiner-based linear regression method. RapidMiner is used as a data mining tool because of its ability to integrate data preprocessing, regression modeling, and model performance evaluation visually and systematically. The results of the study are expected to be able to provide a quantitative overview of the influence of each CPU specification on system performance and produce an accurate prediction model. Thus, this research can be a reference in making decisions about the selection of computer hardware objectively and data-based [5].

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

2.1 Computer System Performance

Computer system performance is the ability of a system to complete computing tasks effectively and efficiently, which is measured through various indicators such as response time, throughput, and the use of system resources. Benchmarking of processor (CPU) performance provides an objective picture of the CPU's ability to handle compute workloads. Research [6] shows that the benchmarking The CPU can accurately map performance differences between hardware configurations, providing an important basis for analyzing the performance of a computer system.

2.2 CPU Specifications as a Performance Determinant

CPU specifications include various technical parameters such as speed Clock, number Core, thread, and size Cache which directly affects the processing ability of instructions. These technical parameters govern how quickly and efficiently the CPU can execute commands, process data, and interact with other components in the system. Research [7] indicates that variations in the number of threads and cores impact the CPU's efficiency in executing compute tasks, which is reflected in changes in CPU execution time and utility during testing.

2.3 CPU Performance Benchmarking and Measurement

Benchmarking is an empirical technique for evaluating CPU performance under a variety of different working conditions and workload scenarios. This method provides performance numbers that describe the CPU's ability to handle real computing. In the study [8], the benchmark results are used as a strong indication that CPUs with different technical specifications produce significant differences in performance scores, thus validating the role of the specification as a determinant factor of system performance.

2.4 Linear Regression as a Quantitative Analysis Method

Linear regression is a quantitative analysis method used to analyze the relationship and influence between independent variables and dependent variables based on statistical numerical data. In the study Analysis of the Influence of CPU Specifications on System Performance Using RapidMiner-Based Linear Regression, linear regression was used to find out the extent to which CPU specifications, such as clock

speed, number of cores, and cache capacity, affect system performance measured through certain parameters. This method is expressed in the form of a mathematical equation that allows researchers to measure the direction and magnitude of the influence of each CPU specification variable on system performance. The use of RapidMiner software helps the linear regression analysis process to be more structured, starting from data processing, model formation, to evaluation of results using statistical indicators, so that the resulting analysis is objective, measurable, and easy to interpret in quantitative research.[9]

2.5 Linear Regression in Data Mining and RapidMiner

RapidMiner is a data mining and machine learning which provides a visual platform to perform predictive analysis, including linear regression, without the need for complex program code writing. In linear regression applications, RapidMiner allows users to perform data preprocessing, model training, and model performance evaluation in an integrated manner. This process improves efficiency in modeling the relationship between input variables (e.g. CPU specifications) and output variables (e.g. benchmark scores or execution times). Relevant studies show that the use of RapidMiner in linear regression provides easy integration of systematic data analysis and improves modeling efficiency and accuracy [10].

2.6 The Relationship between CPU Specifications and System Performance Quantitatively

Several studies in Indonesia show that quantitative approaches, especially linear regression, are effectively used in predicting and analyzing the relationship between technical variables and output indicators. Linear regression analysis can capture the relationship between input factors such as CPU usage and performance outcomes such as task execution time. For example, a linear regression model designed to predict the execution time of computing tasks based on the utilization rate of CPUs and other resources shows that the CPU usage variable has a significant influence on the prediction of execution time, which is relevant to be applied in this study in analyzing the influence of CPU specifications on system performance [11].

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Types and Approaches to Research

This study uses a quantitative approach with the data mining method, because the analysis is carried out on numerical data to identify the statistical relationship between CPU specifications and system performance. The multiple linear regression method is used to determine the influence of several independent variables on one dependent variable simultaneously. The analysis process is carried out with the help of the RapidMiner Studio software, which provides a visual and integrated regression modeling and evaluation facility.

3.2 Definitions and Data Types

The data used in this study are secondary data obtained from the CPU Performance Dataset available in the UCI Machine Learning Repository. This dataset contains CPU hardware specification data as well as CPU relative performance values based on benchmark test results. The data used consisted of 209 observational data with seven numerical attributes representing CPU specifications and system performance.

3.3 Research Variables

The variables used in this study consist of independent variables and dependent variables. Independent variables include MYCT (Machine Cycle Time), MMIN (Minimum Main Memory), MMAX (Maximum Main Memory), CACH (Cache Memory), CHMIN (Minimum Channels), and CHMAX (Maximum Channels) which represent the CPU's technical specifications. The dependent variable used is PRP (Published Relative Performance) which functions as an indicator of the performance of the CPU system.

3.4 Pre-Data Processing Stage

The pre-processing stage of the data is carried out to improve the quality of the data before modeling. At this stage, the missing value contained in several numerical attributes is identified, especially in the variables CACH, CHMIN, and CHMAX. The blank values are handled by the filling method using the mean values of each attribute, because the data is numerical and this method can maintain the characteristics of the data distribution. The entire preprocessing process is done using the operators available on RapidMiner.

3.5 Pemodelan Regresi Linier

Modeling was performed using multiple linear regression with the aim of modeling the relationship between CPU specifications and system performance. The variables MYCT, MMIN, MMAX, CACH, CHMIN, and CHMAX were used as predictor variables, while PRP was used as the response variable. The modeling process is carried out using

the Linear Regression operator on RapidMiner to produce the regression coefficient and the model constant.

3.6 Model Validation and Evaluation

Model validation is carried out using the cross-validation method to ensure that the resulting model does not experience overfitting and has good generalization capabilities. Evaluation of the performance of the linear regression model was carried out using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and determination coefficient (R^2) metrics. The RMSE value is used to measure the rate of prediction error, while the R^2 value indicates how much variation in CPU performance can be explained by the specifications used in the model.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Data

The data is a dataset of CPU specifications used in this study. The attributes used include MYCT, MMIN, MMAX, CACH, CHMIN, and CHMAX as independent variables that represent the characteristics of the CPU hardware, while the class attributes are used as dependent variables that show the value of CPU performance based on the benchmark results. This dataset is numerical and has quite a variety of specifications, so it is suitable for analysis using the linear regression method to determine the influence of CPU specifications on system performance.

Table 1. Actual Data

MYCT	MMIN	MMAX	CACH	CHMIN	CHMAX	Class
125,0	256,0	6000,0	256,0	16,0	128,0	198,0
29,0	8000,0	32000,0	32,0	8,0	32,0	269,0
29,0	8000,0	32000,0	32,0	8,0	32,0	220,0
29,0	8000,0	32000,0	32,0	8,0	32,0	172,0
29,0	8000,0	16000,0	32,0	8,0	16,0	132,0
26,0	8000,0	32000,0	64,0	8,0	32,0	318,0
23,0	16000,0	32000,0	64,0	16,0	32,0	367,0
23,0	16000,0	32000,0	64,0	16,0	32,0	489,0
23,0	16000,0	64000,0	64,0	16,0	32,0	636,0
23,0	32000,0	64000,0	128,0	32,0	64,0	1144,0
400,0	1000,0	3000,0	0,0	1,0	2,0	38,0
400,0	512,0	3500,0	4,0	1,0	6,0	40,0
60,0	2000,0	8000,0	65,0	1,0	8,0	92,0
50,0	4000,0	16000,0	65,0	1,0	8,0	138,0
350,0	64,0	64,0	0,0	1,0	4,0	10,0
200,0	512,0	16000,0	0,0	4,0	32,0	35,0
167,0	524,0	2000,0	8,0	4,0	15,0	19,0
143,0	512,0	5000,0	0,0	7,0	32,0	28,0
143,0	1000,0	2000,0	0,0	5,0	16,0	31,0
110,0	5000,0	5000,0	142,0	8,0	64,0	120,0
143,0	1500,0	6300,0	0,0	5,0	32,0	30,0
143,0	3100,0	6200,0	0,0	5,0	20,0	33,0
143,0	2300,0	6200,0	0,0	6,0	64,0	61,0
110,0	3100,0	6200,0	0,0	6,0	64,0	76,0
320,0	128,0	6000,0	0,0	1,0	12,0	23,0
320,0	512,0	2000,0	4,0	1,0	3,0	69,0
320,0	256,0	6000,0	0,0	1,0	6,0	33,0

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320,0	256,0	3000,0	4,0	1,0	3,0	27,0
320,0	512,0	5000,0	4,0	1,0	5,0	77,0
320,0	256,0	5000,0	4,0	1,0	6,0	27,0
25,0	1310,0	2620,0	131,0	12,0	24,0	274,0
25,0	1310,0	2620,0	131,0	12,0	24,0	368,0
50,0	2620,0	10480,0	30,0	12,0	24,0	32,0
50,0	2620,0	10480,0	30,0	12,0	24,0	63,0
56,0	5240,0	20970,0	30,0	12,0	24,0	106,0
64,0	5240,0	20970,0	30,0	12,0	24,0	208,0
50,0	500,0	2000,0	8,0	1,0	4,0	20,0
50,0	1000,0	4000,0	8,0	1,0	5,0	29,0
50,0	2000,0	8000,0	8,0	1,0	5,0	71,0
50,0	1000,0	4000,0	8,0	3,0	5,0	26,0
50,0	1000,0	8000,0	8,0	3,0	5,0	36,0
50,0	2000,0	16000,0	8,0	3,0	5,0	40,0
50,0	2000,0	16000,0	8,0	3,0	6,0	52,0
50,0	2000,0	16000,0	8,0	3,0	6,0	60,0
133,0	1000,0	12000,0	9,0	3,0	12,0	72,0
133,0	1000,0	8000,0	9,0	3,0	12,0	72,0
810,0	512,0	512,0	8,0	1,0	1,0	18,0
810,0	1000,0	5000,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	20,0
320,0	512,0	8000,0	4,0	1,0	5,0	40,0
200,0	512,0	8000,0	8,0	1,0	8,0	62,0
700,0	384,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	24,0
700,0	256,0	2000,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	24,0
140,0	1000,0	16000,0	16,0	1,0	3,0	138,0
200,0	1000,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	2,0	36,0
110,0	1000,0	4000,0	16,0	1,0	2,0	26,0
110,0	1000,0	12000,0	16,0	1,0	2,0	60,0
220,0	1000,0	8000,0	16,0	1,0	2,0	71,0
800,0	256,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	4,0	12,0
800,0	256,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	4,0	14,0
800,0	256,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	4,0	20,0
800,0	256,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	4,0	16,0
800,0	256,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	4,0	22,0
125,0	512,0	1000,0	0,0	8,0	20,0	36,0
75,0	2000,0	8000,0	64,0	1,0	38,0	144,0
75,0	2000,0	16000,0	64,0	1,0	38,0	144,0
75,0	2000,0	16000,0	128,0	1,0	38,0	259,0
90,0	256,0	1000,0	0,0	3,0	10,0	17,0
105,0	256,0	2000,0	0,0	3,0	10,0	26,0
105,0	1000,0	4000,0	0,0	3,0	24,0	32,0
105,0	2000,0	4000,0	8,0	3,0	19,0	32,0
75,0	2000,0	8000,0	8,0	3,0	24,0	62,0
75,0	3000,0	8000,0	8,0	3,0	48,0	64,0
175,0	256,0	2000,0	0,0	3,0	24,0	22,0
300,0	768,0	3000,0	0,0	6,0	24,0	36,0
300,0	768,0	3000,0	6,0	6,0	24,0	44,0
300,0	768,0	12000,0	6,0	6,0	24,0	50,0
300,0	768,0	4500,0	0,0	1,0	24,0	45,0
300,0	384,0	12000,0	6,0	1,0	24,0	53,0
300,0	192,0	768,0	6,0	6,0	24,0	36,0
180,0	768,0	12000,0	6,0	1,0	31,0	84,0
330,0	1000,0	3000,0	0,0	2,0	4,0	16,0
300,0	1000,0	4000,0	8,0	3,0	64,0	38,0

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300,0	1000,0	16000,0	8,0	2,0	112,0	38,0
330,0	1000,0	2000,0	0,0	1,0	2,0	16,0
330,0	1000,0	4000,0	0,0	3,0	6,0	22,0
140,0	2000,0	4000,0	0,0	3,0	6,0	29,0
140,0	2000,0	4000,0	0,0	4,0	8,0	40,0
140,0	2000,0	4000,0	8,0	1,0	20,0	35,0
140,0	2000,0	32000,0	32,0	1,0	20,0	134,0
140,0	2000,0	8000,0	32,0	1,0	54,0	66,0
140,0	2000,0	32000,0	32,0	1,0	54,0	141,0
140,0	2000,0	32000,0	32,0	1,0	54,0	189,0
140,0	2000,0	4000,0	8,0	1,0	20,0	22,0
57,0	4000,0	16000,0	1,0	6,0	12,0	132,0
57,0	4000,0	24000,0	64,0	12,0	16,0	237,0
26,0	16000,0	32000,0	64,0	16,0	24,0	465,0
26,0	16000,0	32000,0	64,0	8,0	24,0	465,0
26,0	8000,0	32000,0	0,0	8,0	24,0	277,0
26,0	8000,0	16000,0	0,0	8,0	16,0	185,0
480,0	96,0	512,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	6,0
203,0	1000,0	2000,0	0,0	1,0	5,0	24,0
115,0	512,0	6000,0	16,0	1,0	6,0	45,0
1100,0	512,0	1500,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	7,0
1100,0	768,0	2000,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	13,0
600,0	768,0	2000,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	16,0
400,0	2000,0	4000,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	32,0
400,0	4000,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	1,0	32,0
900,0	1000,0	1000,0	0,0	1,0	2,0	11,0
900,0	512,0	1000,0	0,0	1,0	2,0	11,0
900,0	1000,0	4000,0	4,0	1,0	2,0	18,0
900,0	1000,0	4000,0	8,0	1,0	2,0	22,0
900,0	2000,0	4000,0	0,0	3,0	6,0	37,0
225,0	2000,0	4000,0	8,0	3,0	6,0	40,0
225,0	2000,0	4000,0	8,0	3,0	6,0	34,0
180,0	2000,0	8000,0	8,0	1,0	6,0	50,0
185,0	2000,0	16000,0	16,0	1,0	6,0	76,0
180,0	2000,0	16000,0	16,0	1,0	6,0	66,0
225,0	1000,0	4000,0	2,0	3,0	6,0	24,0
25,0	2000,0	12000,0	8,0	1,0	4,0	49,0
25,0	2000,0	12000,0	16,0	3,0	5,0	66,0
17,0	4000,0	16000,0	8,0	6,0	12,0	100,0
17,0	4000,0	16000,0	32,0	6,0	12,0	133,0
1500,0	768,0	1000,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	12,0
1500,0	768,0	2000,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	18,0
800,0	768,0	2000,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	20,0
50,0	2000,0	4000,0	0,0	3,0	6,0	27,0
50,0	2000,0	8000,0	8,0	3,0	6,0	45,0
50,0	2000,0	8000,0	8,0	1,0	6,0	56,0
50,0	2000,0	16000,0	24,0	1,0	6,0	70,0
50,0	2000,0	16000,0	24,0	1,0	6,0	80,0
50,0	8000,0	16000,0	48,0	1,0	10,0	136,0
100,0	1000,0	8000,0	0,0	2,0	6,0	16,0
100,0	1000,0	8000,0	24,0	2,0	6,0	26,0
100,0	1000,0	8000,0	24,0	3,0	6,0	32,0
50,0	2000,0	16000,0	12,0	3,0	16,0	45,0
50,0	2000,0	16000,0	24,0	6,0	16,0	54,0
50,0	2000,0	16000,0	24,0	6,0	16,0	65,0

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150,0	512,0	4000,0	0,0	8,0	128,0	30,0
115,0	2000,0	8000,0	16,0	1,0	3,0	50,0
115,0	2000,0	4000,0	2,0	1,0	5,0	40,0
92,0	2000,0	8000,0	32,0	1,0	6,0	62,0
92,0	2000,0	8000,0	32,0	1,0	6,0	60,0
92,0	2000,0	8000,0	4,0	1,0	6,0	50,0
75,0	4000,0	16000,0	16,0	1,0	6,0	66,0
60,0	4000,0	16000,0	32,0	1,0	6,0	86,0
60,0	2000,0	16000,0	64,0	5,0	8,0	74,0
60,0	4000,0	16000,0	64,0	5,0	8,0	93,0
50,0	4000,0	16000,0	64,0	5,0	10,0	111,0
72,0	4000,0	16000,0	64,0	8,0	16,0	143,0
72,0	2000,0	8000,0	16,0	6,0	8,0	105,0
40,0	8000,0	16000,0	32,0	8,0	16,0	214,0
40,0	8000,0	32000,0	64,0	8,0	24,0	277,0
35,0	8000,0	32000,0	64,0	8,0	24,0	370,0
38,0	16000,0	32000,0	128,0	16,0	32,0	510,0
48,0	4000,0	24000,0	32,0	8,0	24,0	214,0
38,0	8000,0	32000,0	64,0	8,0	24,0	326,0
30,0	16000,0	32000,0	256,0	16,0	24,0	510,0
112,0	1000,0	1000,0	0,0	1,0	4,0	8,0
84,0	1000,0	2000,0	0,0	1,0	6,0	12,0
56,0	1000,0	4000,0	0,0	1,0	6,0	17,0
56,0	2000,0	6000,0	0,0	1,0	8,0	21,0
56,0	2000,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	8,0	24,0
56,0	4000,0	8000,0	0,0	1,0	8,0	34,0
56,0	4000,0	12000,0	0,0	1,0	8,0	42,0
56,0	4000,0	16000,0	0,0	1,0	8,0	46,0
38,0	4000,0	8000,0	32,0	16,0	32,0	51,0
38,0	4000,0	8000,0	32,0	16,0	32,0	116,0
38,0	8000,0	16000,0	64,0	4,0	8,0	100,0
38,0	8000,0	24000,0	160,0	4,0	8,0	140,0
38,0	4000,0	16000,0	128,0	16,0	32,0	212,0
200,0	1000,0	2000,0	0,0	1,0	2,0	25,0
200,0	1000,0	4000,0	0,0	1,0	4,0	30,0
200,0	2000,0	8000,0	64,0	1,0	5,0	41,0
250,0	512,0	4000,0	0,0	1,0	7,0	25,0
250,0	512,0	4000,0	0,0	4,0	7,0	50,0
250,0	1000,0	16000,0	1,0	1,0	8,0	50,0
160,0	512,0	4000,0	2,0	1,0	5,0	30,0
160,0	512,0	2000,0	2,0	3,0	8,0	32,0
160,0	1000,0	4000,0	8,0	1,0	14,0	38,0
160,0	1000,0	8000,0	16,0	1,0	14,0	60,0
160,0	2000,0	8000,0	32,0	1,0	13,0	109,0
240,0	512,0	1000,0	8,0	1,0	3,0	6,0
240,0	512,0	2000,0	8,0	1,0	5,0	11,0
105,0	2000,0	4000,0	8,0	3,0	8,0	22,0
105,0	2000,0	6000,0	16,0	6,0	16,0	33,0
105,0	2000,0	8000,0	16,0	4,0	14,0	58,0
52,0	4000,0	16000,0	32,0	4,0	12,0	130,0
70,0	4000,0	12000,0	8,0	6,0	8,0	75,0
59,0	4000,0	12000,0	32,0	6,0	12,0	113,0
59,0	8000,0	16000,0	64,0	12,0	24,0	188,0
26,0	8000,0	24000,0	32,0	8,0	16,0	173,0
26,0	8000,0	32000,0	64,0	12,0	16,0	248,0

26,0	8000,0	32000,0	128,0	24,0	32,0	405,0
116,0	2000,0	8000,0	32,0	5,0	28,0	70,0
50,0	2000,0	32000,0	24,0	6,0	26,0	114,0
50,0	2000,0	32000,0	48,0	26,0	52,0	208,0
50,0	2000,0	32000,0	112,0	52,0	104,0	307,0
50,0	4000,0	32000,0	112,0	52,0	104,0	397,0
30,0	8000,0	64000,0	96,0	12,0	176,0	915,0

4.2 Linear Regression Analysis Results

Table 2. Results of Linear Regression Coefficient Analysis
Attribute Coefficient Std. Error t-Stat p-Value

MYCT	0.026	0.018	1.436	0.153	
MMIN	0.010	0.002	4.650	0.000	
MMA	0.005	0.001	7.842	0.000	
CACH	1.230	0.154	7.992	0.000	
CHMIN	0.452	0.118	3.831	0.000	
CHMAX		0.778	0.201	3.866	0.000
Intercept	-35.488	8.772	-4.045	0.000	

From the table above, it can be seen that five of the six independent variables show a very significant influence on the dependent variable (class), with a p-value of 0.000. The MMA variable has the highest standard coefficient (0.429 based on previous output), indicating that maximum memory speed contributes the most to improved system performance. Followed by CACH (0.343), MMIN (0.234), and CHMAX (0.163).

The resulting linear regression equation is:

$$\text{Class} = -35,488 + 0,026(\text{MYCT}) + 0,010(\text{MMIN}) + 0,005(\text{MMA}) + 1,230(\text{CACH}) + 0,452(\text{CHMIN}) + 0,778(\text{CHMAX})$$

The MYCT (Machine Cycle Time) variable was not statistically significant (p-value = 0.153), which indicates that machine cycle time did not have a significant influence on predicting system performance based on this model. This may be due to technological developments where the engine cycle factor is no longer the main determinant of the performance of modern systems.

4.3 Model Performance Evaluation

PerformanceVector

```
PerformanceVector:
root_mean_squared_error: 72.696 +/- 0.000
```

Figure 1. Verformance Vector

Model performance evaluation was conducted using the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) metric. An RMSE value of 72.696 indicates the average error of the model's prediction of the actual value. To assess the quality of these values, it is necessary to consider the scale of the dependent variables. In this context, an RMSE value of 72.696 indicates that the model has a fairly significant error rate, but it is still acceptable depending on the purpose of the application and the expected error tolerance.

4.4 Prediction Result Analysis

The model's prediction results show a pattern consistent with the linear relationship between the predictor and target variables. The CACH variable has the largest coefficient (1,230), indicating that each increase of one unit in the cache

memory will increase the predicted performance by 1,230 units, assuming the other variables are fixed. This is in line with computer architecture theory that emphasizes the importance of cache memory in improving system performance.

The MMA variable although having a small coefficient (0.005), makes an important contribution due to the large-scale value of this variable in the dataset. A standard coefficient of 0.429 confirms that MMA is the strongest predictor in the model.

5. CLOSING

Based on the results of the linear regression analysis that has been carried out, it can be identified that the MMA variable (maximum main memory capacity) has the most dominant influence on system performance with a standard coefficient of 0.429. This shows that in the context of the computer systems being analyzed, the system's ability to support large memory capacity is a major determining factor that affects overall performance. These findings are in line with the basic principle of computer architecture that adequate memory capacity allows the system to handle more complex workloads and hold more data in the process of program execution.

On the other hand, the CACH variable (cache memory capacity) although it has the largest regression coefficient in absolute terms (1.230), its relative contribution in the model is slightly lower than that of MMA with a standard coefficient of 0.343. This phenomenon can be explained by the role of cache memory as a high-speed memory that serves as a buffer between the processor and the main memory, so that although the impact per unit is large, the overall impact on system performance is slightly lower than the main memory capacity. This suggests that in the context of this dataset, the scale of available cache capacity may be more limited than the variation in primary memory capacity.

The results of the study showing the insignificance of the MYCT variable (machine cycle time) provide important insights into the evolution of computer technology. Although theoretically machine cycle time should be inversely proportional to system performance, its insignificance in this model may reflect that in the era of the computer systems represented by this dataset, the memory and cache capacity factors have become more critical than the cycle speed of the processor itself. Another possibility is that the variation in MYCT values in the dataset is not large enough to show a statistically significant influence, or that there are complex interactions with other variables that are not captured by a simple linear model.

The RMSE value of 72.696 which represents an average prediction error of 68.8% of the target mean reveals the limitations of the linear regression model in capturing the complexity of the relationship between hardware

specifications and system performance. This high error rate indicates that although the model is successful in identifying significant variables, its predictive capabilities are still limited for applications that require high accuracy. Possible causes include non-linear relationships between variables, complex interactions that are not modeled, or additional explanatory variables that are not included in the analysis such as processor architecture type, bus speed, or other system configurations.

From a practical perspective, this model retains its application value as an initial estimation tool for estimating system performance based on basic hardware configurations. The finding that maximum memory capacity is the strongest predictor provides valuable guidance in decision-making regarding system specifications, particularly in budget allocation for hardware components. However, for the need for more precise predictions, a more sophisticated modeling approach is needed that is able to capture more complex relationships and include additional explanatory variables that are relevant to the context of modern computer systems.

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